

The Impact of Education and Training and Career Development on the Performance of Bank Syariah Indonesia Employees

Rifa'atul Maftuhah
Universitas Muhammadiyah
Surabaya

Abstract:- Education and training is one form of program that can be carried out by a company to improve employee knowledge and skills. According to Mursidi (2009:121) education and training can provide guidance for employees in behaving and acting so that problems at work are resolved appropriately. According to Prajitiasari (2012:1) education and training also provide an increase in employee work productivity.

Employee performance is the synergy result of the organization's internal and external environmental factors, as well as employee internal factors (Wirawan, 2009). Employee performance is a form of employee confidence in their behavior and contribution to organizational achievement Ahmad & Shahzad, 2011). Performance is also defined as the result of a certain work process at a planned time and place (Mangkuprawira & Hubeis, 2007). Dessler (2010) states that performance appraisals are conducted by setting performance standards, implementing performance appraisals, and providing feedback.

Education and training have an effect on the performance of Bank Syariah Indonesia employees" answered from the results of the t-count value of 4.783 with a significance level of more than 5%, namely 0.000 in the education and training variables. career development has an effect on the performance of Bank Syariah Indonesia employees" answered from the results of the t-count value of 4.287 with a significance level of more than 5%, namely 0.021 in the career development variable. Education and training as well as career development have an effect on the performance of Indonesian Sharia Bank Employees" answered from the results of the t-count value of 18,750 with a significance level of more than 5%, namely 0.00.

Keywords:- Education and training, career development, employee performance.

I. INTRODUCTION

Education and training is one form of program that can be carried out by a company to improve employee knowledge and skills. According to Mursidi (2009:121) education and training can provide guidance for employees in behaving and acting so that problems at work are resolved appropriately. According to Prajitiasari (2012:1) education and training also provide an increase in employee work productivity.

Mufidah et al. (2014:1341) said that education is an individual preparation program to know, recognize and develop a more systematic way of thinking while training is an implementation that involves many things such as learning, better work practices, as well as the experience that will be experienced by employees. Then Notoatmodjo (1998) said that training generally emphasizes psychomotor abilities, although it is based on knowledge and attitudes, while education emphasizes cognitive, effective and psychomotor abilities that require balanced attention. Harrison (2005) also argues that workforce training has become an urgent need for all organizations in developing countries.

In addition to obtaining education and training, employees or workers also wish to obtain a better job position than the previous one. To get a better job position, the workforce needs career development with the potential that exists within them. Employees who have the potential or ability, both individual abilities and the ability to work in teams will be able to work well in achieving company goals, so this must be a concern for the company. Ma'mun (2013: 505) says that career development is important for employees in carrying out their main duties and functions so that work needs and organizational goals can be realized. Employees who are given the opportunity to develop their careers will always work optimally for the advancement of the company. Career development has become a necessity that must be accepted by employees in addition to salary or bonuses. According to Oduma and Were (2014:2), the better standard of living makes employees not only want the usual jobs and benefits, but they also want a career that can open up their interests, personalities, abilities that are in harmony with all employee life situations.

There are several organizations that have carried out career development but more organizations have not carried out career development programs. Royley and Jackson (2012:17) say that some organizations have carried out career development programs well but at the same time more organizations have not implemented career development programs. According to Agba et al. (2010:106) more attention to career development, should be given by most organizations. Therefore, companies need to carry out career development programs and play a role in providing all the needs needed by employees so that employee performance can continue to increase.

Education and training as well as career development are some of the things that can support employee performance. According to Sultana et al. (2012:647) performance is the realization of certain tasks on accuracy, completeness, cost and speed with standards that have been measured or identified. Good performance is the main factor so that the company can compete with other companies. Khairiyah and Annisa (2013: 323) also say that improving employee performance can provide progress for companies to survive in an increasingly unstable business competition. Therefore, companies need to try to improve employee performance continuously to get better quality performance so that the company's goals that have been set previously can be achieved and the integrity of the company can be maintained.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. Education and Training

According to Yohanas (2007: 19) education and training programs are one of the most important activities regarding human resources in facing various company challenges, both now and in the future. Meanwhile, according to Mumus (2013) education and training is a process of teaching the skills needed by employees to do their jobs.

B. Career development

According to Hady (2013) that career development can be said to be a condition that indicates an increase in a person's status in the organization in the career path set in the organization concerned. Meanwhile, career development (Bahri, 2016) is an effort or steps carried out by an employee and/or by a human resource leader in the context of developing the potential of employees to be able to

occupy higher positions in an effort to achieve company goals.

C. Performance

Employee performance is the synergy result of the organization's internal and external environmental factors, as well as employee internal factors (Wirawan, 2009). Employee performance is a form of employee confidence in their behavior and contribution to organizational achievement Ahmad & Shahzad, 2011). Performance is also defined as the result of a certain work process at a planned time and place (Mangkuprawira & Hubeis, 2007). Dessler (2010) states that performance appraisal is conducted by setting performance standards, implementing performance appraisals, and providing feedback.

D. Hypothesis

- There is an influence between education and training on the performance of Bank Syariah Indonesia employees
- There is an influence between career development on the performance of Bank Syariah Indonesia employees
- There is an influence between education and training and career development on the performance of Bank Syariah Indonesia employees

III. RESEARCH AND METHODOLOGY

The object of this quantitative research is Syaria Indonesia Banking in Surabaya City, where all of its employees are the research population and 250 of them are selected as samples through purposive sampling technique with the criteria that they are permanent employees in Syaria Indonesia Banking in Surabaya City. The types of data used are primary data and secondary data. Primary data is collected using a G-form questionnaire technique which is a close-ended question, and then measured using a Likert scale. Meanwhile, secondary data was collected through documentation techniques. Data analysis is conducted using descriptive analysis methods and SPSS software. The variables and indicator:

No	Variabel	Indicators
1.	Education and Training	Implementation Evaluation Implementation
2.	Career development	1)Quality 2) Timeframe 3) Presence 4) Cooperation
3.	Performance	Quality of work 2) Working quantity 3) Discipline 4) Initiative 5) Responsibility

Tabel 1: Variabel and Indicators

The multiple linear regression formula used is:

$$Y = b_0 + b_1 X_1 + b_2 X_2 + e_i$$

Y	= Employee Performance
b_0	= Constant
b_1 & b_2	= Correlation coefficient for each variable
X_1	= Education and Training
X_2	= Career Development Variable
e_i	= Disturbing factor/error

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Classical Assumption Test

a) Normality test

This normality test is used to determine whether or not the distribution of research is normal for each research variable. The normality test of the data in this study used the P-Plot normality test. The results of the normality test on the residuals are as follows:

Picture 1: Normality test

The results of the normality test in the image above show that the residual form is close to the normal curve or the p-plot graph. It can be seen that the points are close to the 45 degree line on the curve or close to a straight line, so that the residual data are normally distributed.

B. Multicollinearity Test

Multicollinearity test means that the independent variables contained in the regression model have a perfect linear relationship or detect perfect (high correlation coefficient or even 1). To find out whether there is multicollinearity, look at the tolerance and VIF values. The following are the results of the multicollinearity test:

No.	Variabel	Tolerance	VIF
1.	Education and Training	0,843	1,186
2.	Career Development	0,843	1,186

Tabel 2: Tolerance and VIF Values

Based on the table above, it can be seen that the tolerance value and VIF have no tolerance value below 0.10 (tolerance value of 0.843), as well as no VIF value above 10 (VIF value of 1.186).

C. Heteroscedasticity Test

Heteroscedasticity is the residual variance that is not the same for all observations in the regression model. A good regression should not occur heteroscedasticity. Heteroscedasticity testing in this study used the Scatterplot test technique as follows:

Picture 2: Scatterplot

Based on the scatterplot output above, it can be seen that the points are spread out and do not form a certain clear pattern, so it can be concluded that there is no heteroscedasticity problem.

D. Linearity Test

This linearity test aims to determine whether the distribution of the data has a distribution that matches the linear line by looking at the Anova table on the sig. Here are the results of the linearity test:

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	252.112	2	126.056	18.750	.000 ^b
	Residual	1660.592	247	6.723		
	Total	1912.704	249			

a. Dependent Variable: Kinerja Karyawan
 b. Predictors: (Constant), Pengembangan Karir, Pendidikan dan Pelatihan

Tabel 3: Linearity Test

Based on table 2 above, it shows that the sig value of the education and training and career development variables is 0.000, this indicates that the value is <0.05, which means that there is a linear relationship between the variables of education and training and career development.

a) Multiple linear regression equation
 The results of data processing with multiple linear regression models can be seen in the following table:

Variabel	Koefisien Regresi
Konstanta	15,029
Pendidikan dan pelatihan (X1)	0,198
Pengembangan karir (X2)	0,167

Tabel 4: Multiple linear regression equation

$$Y = 15,029 + 0,198X_1 + 0,167X_2 + e_i$$

From the regression equation, then:

- The resulting constant (a) is 15,029, this indicates that the amount of employee performance is 15,029, if the variables of education and training and career development are constant zero.
- The regression coefficient for the education and training variable (X1) is 0.198, this indicates that every change in the education and training variable (X1) will have a positive effect on employee performance (Y). The value of the positive regression coefficient indicates the effect that arises in the same direction, where the increase in the education and training variables is by one unit, the employee's performance will increase by one with the assumption that career development is constant.

- The regression coefficient for career development variable (X2) is 0.167, this indicates that every change in career development variable (X2) will have a positive effect on employee performance (Y). The positive regression coefficient value shows the effect that arises in the same direction, where the increase in the career development variable is one unit, the employee's performance will increase by one with the assumption that education and training are constant.

b) Hypothesis Testing Process
 Hypothesis testing in this research includes partial test and simultaneous test.

a. Partial Test (t-test)
 T test is used to determine the effect of education and training and career development partially on employee performance. The results of the t test are as follows:

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	15.029	1.696		8.864	.000
	Pendidikan dan Pelatihan	.198	.041	.309	4.783	.000
	Pengembangan Karir	.167	.048	.314	4.287	.021

a. Dependent Variable: Kinerja Karyawan

Tabel 5: Partial Test (t-test)

The explanation in table 5 can be described as follows:

- The t-count value for the Education and training variable (X1) is 4.783 with a significance level greater than 5%, which is 0.000. This means that education and training partially have a significant effect on employee performance.
- The calculated t value for the career development variable (X2) is 4.287 with a significance level greater than 5%, namely 0.021, meaning that career development partially

has a significant effect on employee performance. Increased career development improves employee performance.

b. F test

The F test is used to test the effect of education and training variables as well as career development simultaneously on employee performance. The results of the F test are as follows:

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	252.112	2	126.056	18.750	.000 ^b
	Residual	1660.592	247	6.723		
	Total	1912.704	249			

a. Dependent Variable: Kinerja Karyawan

b. Predictors: (Constant), Pengembangan Karir, Pendidikan dan Pelatihan

Table 6: F Test

Based on the table above that the variables of education and training as well as career development have a simultaneous effect on employee performance. This can be seen from the calculated F value, which is 18.750 with a significance value of $p = 0.000 < 0.05$.

c) Hypothesis Test

To find out whether the hypothesis proposed by the author was answered or not in this study, based on the results of the above data processing, it was concluded as follows:

- Hypothesis 1, namely "education and training have an effect on the performance of Bank Syariah Indonesia employees" was answered from the results of the t-count value of 4.783 with a significance level of more than 5%, namely 0.000 on the education and training variable. This shows that education and training partially affect employee performance so that hypothesis 1 is accepted.
- Hypothesis 2, namely "career development has an effect on the performance of Indonesian Sharia Bank Employees" was answered from the results of the t-count value of 4.287 with a significance level of more than 5%, namely 0.021 on the career development variable. This shows that environmental career development partially affects employee performance so that hypothesis 2 is accepted.
- Hypothesis 3, namely "Education and training and career development affect the performance of Bank Syariah Indonesia employees" answered from the results of the t-count of 18,750 with a significance level of more than 5%, namely 0.00.

V. DISCUSSION

Education and training are very important to do because both are ways used by organizations to maintain, maintain, maintain employees in the organization as well as improve employee skills in improving their performance. Education provides provisions in the form of a theoretical understanding of a job, so that employees can better understand their duties in the workplace. the latest level of education held by the employee is in accordance with the qualifications of the position occupied and adjusts the formal education possessed by the employee in accordance with the field of work faced by the employee. The results of this study are in accordance with the opinion of Sutrisno (2011:65), education as the totality of human interaction for the development of a whole person, and education is a continuous process that is constantly evolving, and is faced with the problem of limited resources, therefore it is necessary to implement a management system that enable the success of the educational mission.

Education and training as well as career development are some of the things that can support employee performance. According to Sultana et al. (2012:647) performance is the realization of certain tasks on accuracy, completeness, cost and speed with standards that have been measured or identified. Good performance is the main factor so that the company can compete with other companies. Khairiyah and Annisa (2013: 323) also say that improving employee performance can provide progress for companies to survive in an increasingly unstable business competition. Therefore, companies need to try to improve employee performance continuously to get better quality performance so that the company's goals that have been set previously can be achieved and the integrity of the company can be maintained.

Based on the results of this study, there are several policy suggestions that are very likely to be taken at the Directorate General of Intellectual Property Rights, namely that education and training participants must have clear criteria and based on the results of performance evaluations. Career development must be managed and implemented as well as possible and clearly. In addition to paying attention to educational background and seniority in career development, one must also pay attention to the performance of the employee concerned. Employee discipline must be carried out by increasing the responsibility of the employee's direct supervisor, using a progressive method and having tolerance to certain limits.

Based on the research results of Yakub et al. (2014) showed the results that education and training had a positive and significant effect on employee performance and also research conducted by Wiguna (2015) showed the results that education and training had a positive and significant effect on employee performance.

However, the results of research by Saranani (2015) showed that education and training had a negative and insignificant effect on employee performance and also research conducted by Jayasuriya (1998) showed that education and training had no significant effect on the performance of health staff. Research conducted by Parerung et al. (2014) said that career development has a positive and significant impact on employee performance and research conducted by Kaseger (2013) shows the results that career development has a positive and significant impact on employee performance. Then research conducted by Oduma and Were (2014) shows that career development has a significant effect on employee performance.

However, research from Shaputra and Hendriani (2015) shows that career development has a negative and insignificant effect on employee performance. Research conducted by Waleed and Fais (2016) regarding the effect of job satisfaction on employee performance shows a positive and significant effect, then research conducted by Langi et al. (2015) shows that job satisfaction has a positive and significant effect on employee performance. However, research from Crossman & Zaki (2003) states that job satisfaction has no significant effect on performance.

The important thing in managing human resources is about employee performance. Employee performance as a result of work in quality and quantity that can be achieved by an employee in carrying out tasks in accordance with the responsibilities given to him. Things that can support the performance of these employees are career development and employee welfare. Career development is intended so that employees have higher abilities than previously possessed abilities so that they can know their functions and roles and responsibilities in the work environment. With career development is also expected to achieve higher performance. The agency strives to foster healthy performance where the rights and obligations of employees are regulated in such a way as to align with the functions, roles and responsibilities of their employees so that employees can participate in the organization. Based on this,

the better employee career development and employee welfare, the higher the employee's performance.

According to Vethzal Rivai (2011: 2013) concludes that there is a positive influence suggesting a positive and significant influence between career development and welfare on employee performance. So it can be concluded that the better the career development and welfare of employees, the better the performance of employees in an agency.

VI. CONCLUSION

- Positive education and training on the performance of Bank Syariah Indonesia employees. It means that education and training partially have a significant positive effect on employee performance, which means if the education and training variable (X1) increases, employee performance will also increase with the assumption that the career development variable is constant. These findings are supported by several indicators, namely the implementation of education and training, evaluation and implementation can improve employee performance so that the training obtained can support their work.
- Career development has a positive effect on the performance of Bank Syariah Indonesia employees. It means that career development partially has a significant positive effect on employee performance, which means that if the career development variable increases, employee performance will also increase with the assumption that the education and training variables are constant. The findings show that career development by looking at the quality of employee work, discipline, and being able to work in a team so as to improve the performance of Bank Syariah Indonesia employees.
- Education and training as well as career development have a positive effect on the performance of Bank Syariah Indonesia employees. This means that education and training as well as career development simultaneously have a significant effect on employee performance. The better the quality of education and training provided to employees as well as career development (career paths) that are definitely in accordance with government regulations, the performance of employees will increase.

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